

“Biophilic” Urbanism, Cities and Nature in East Asia.

Hangzhou & Singapore

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For most of human history, we lived as a part of natural systems and coevolved with other living organisms. Only through industrialization have cities proliferated globally, and our urban environments have increasingly become denser and more compact, gradually abstracted from nature. Today, more than half of the global population is urban, and the urban economy generates more than 80% of global GDP (The World Bank, 2018). This unprecedented growth has not only altered how we live but also directed human history into a new urban era. While the concentration of resources has led to an unprecedented accumulation of opportunities, transforming contemporary cities into global powerhouses of social, economic, scientific and technological developments, contemporary urbanization, to some extent, has become urban modification which further diminishes the possibilities of human contact with nature in urbanized environments, turning cities into concrete deserts. Along with our increasingly unsustainable urban environments lacking ecological stabilities, the absence of nature in our cities has also decreased urban livability and affected the health and well-being of all urbanists, humans, and other living organisms.

Harvard entomologist Edward O. Wilson introduced “Biophilia Hypothesis” with Stephen R. Kellert in their book, *The Biophilia Hypothesis* (1993), which proposed that humans have an innate tendency to seek affiliations with natural environments and other forms of life (Wilson, 1993). The term “Biophilia,” which literally means “love for life” by etymology, was earlier used by American Social Psychoanalyst Erich Fromm in his book, *The Heart of Man: Its Genius for Good and Evil* (1964), to mean “love for humanity and nature, and independence and freedom.” Wilson also used the term in *Biophilia* (1984) to mean “the urge to affiliate with other forms of life,” and has popularized it since. Closely related to evolutionary psychology since the early proposal of the hypothesis, many believe that over millennia of co-evolution humans have developed psychological and physiological needs for regular experience with nature, and such needs are deeply rooted in our biology. In other words, regular contact with nature is essential to the health and well-being of humanity as a species, in addition to the benefits of having ecologically sustainable living environments. As Stephen R. Kellert mentioned in *Birthright: People and Nature in the Modern World* (2012), “we will never be truly healthy, satisfied, or fulfilled if we lived apart and alienated from the environment which we evolved.” Recently, researches from social, psychological, pedagogical, and other areas have further supported this belief that regular exposure to nature has physical, emotional, and cognitive benefits in addition to increasing the sense of happiness.

Evolved from Biophilia Hypothesis, Biophilic Urbanism is a new model of city-making that emerge in response to contemporary urban challenges. Drawing inspiration from the hypothesis, Biophilic Urbanism considers nature as a remedy to contemporary urban issues, such as environmental health, faced by our cities today. Biophilic Urbanism believes “a biophilic city is a green city, a city with abundant nature and natural systems that are visible and accessible to urbanites” (Beatley, 2011). Biophilic Urbanism promotes the relationships of cohabitation among all urban dwellers, humans and other life forms as a symbiotic mutualism relationship, in which all urban dwellers interact to share mutual benefits of living in sustainable and healthy urban environments. It advocates that for urban lives, contacting with nature “is not optional but essential” (Beatley, 2011).

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The "Biophilia Hypothesis" is relatively modern, but the human desire to connect with natural environments has long been embedded in our psyche. Due to millennia of philosophical influence in East Asia, there is a belief that humanity (as a species) is essentially a part of a larger ecosystem, and therefore, the human-made environment should harmoniously embed in the eco-system. Cities, therefore, integrate human-made urban environments into their indigenous ecological systems for shared benefits of sustainable and healthy urban environments to all urban dwellers, humans, and other living organisms. Both Singapore and Hangzhou, as examples, are rising modern metropolises renowned for their biophilic urban environments that contain rich urban biodiversity and elaborated urban landscape systems. The rapid industrialization of both cities during the last half-century has facilitated unprecedented urban growth, while increasingly urbanized environments have also further destabilized their urban ecological systems and isolated urbanists far from their external ecological environments. Environmental sustainability has been a decades-long theme of urban development in both cities. The journeys towards urbanization in both Singapore and Hangzhou are also journeys to restore nature, building biophilic urban environments where human species and other urban living organisms can cohabitate.

To start with, Singapore first introduced its version of the "Garden City" to compensate for the loss of primary forests due to the intensive demands of urbanization in the country's early history. From "Garden City" to "City in a Garden," over the last half-century, Singapore has built an island-wide green network that consists of urban landscapes and biodiversity with systematic planning. This island-wide infrastructure system has since served as an effective eco-strategy to soften the environmental harshness of Singapore as a tropical metropolis. Alternatively, the "Landscape City" Hangzhou is recognized as a prototype of urban and landscape design in the Chinese Cultural Sphere as the built environment of the city has well-integrated into its human-made urban environment over thousands of years of coevolution with the indigenous ecological and geological systems. Therefore, the city grew into its external environments and formed an idealized symbiotic cohabitation, representing the shared belief that the unbuilt urban systems, such as the urban landscape, are equally essential to urban lives as the built.

This paper outlines the characteristics of contemporary urbanization in Singapore and Hangzhou in relation to the concept of Biophilic Urbanism through detailed case studies and comparison of the social and ecological relationships within the built environments and natural systems of both cities. It thus seeks to rethink the relationship between nature and human in our cities and understand how landscape can engage as a medium to reunite nature and human habitats and, eventually, redirect our cities towards more sustainable and livable futures in this new geological era wherein human activities have a dominant influence on global geology and ecological change.